

ON γ - CONNECTEDNESS IN L-TOPOLOGICAL SPACES

P. Senthil Kumar* & S. Sangeetha**

* Assistant Professor, Department of Mathematics, Raja Serfoji Government College,
 Thanjavur, Tamilnadu

** Research Scholar, Department of Mathematics, Raja Serfoji Government College,
 Thanjavur, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: P. Senthil Kumar & S. Sangeetha, "On γ - Connectedness in L-Topological Spaces", International Journal of Advanced Trends in Engineering and Technology, Volume 3, Issue 1, Page Number 168-170, 2018.

Abstract:

In this paper, a certain new connectedness of L-fuzzy subsets in L-topological spaces is introduced and studied by means of γ - closed sets. It preserves some fundamental properties of connected set in general topology. Especially the famous K. Fan's Theorem holds.

1. Introduction:

Connectivity is one of the important notions in general topology, There have been many works about connectedness in L-topological spaces (see [1, 2, 3, 6, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14 etc]. In this paper, we introduce a certain new connectedness in L-topological spaces by means of γ -closed sets, which is called γ -connectedness. The γ - connectedness preserves some fundamental properties of connected sets in general topology. Especially the famous K-Fan's Theorem holds for γ -connectedness.

2. Preliminaries:

Throughout this paper, (L, \vee, \wedge) is a complete De Morgan algebra, X a nonempty set. L^X the set of all L -fuzzy sets on X . The smallest element and the largest element in L^X are denoted by $\underline{0}$ and $\underline{1}$. An element a in L is called a prime element if $a \geq b \wedge c$ implies that $b \leq a$ or $a \leq c$. An element a in L is called a co-prime element if a' is a prime element [5]. The set of all nonzero co-prime elements in L is denoted by $\gamma M(L)$. The set of all nonzero co-prime elements in L^X is denoted by $M(L^X)$. For an L-fuzzy set D , $M(D)$ denotes the set of all nonzero co-prime elements contained in D . An L-topological space is a pair (X, τ) , where τ is a subfamily of L^X which contains $\underline{0}, \underline{1}$ and is closed for any suprema and finite infima. τ is called an L-topology on X . Each member of τ is called an open L-set and its complementation is called a closed L-set. An L'-topological space is an ordered pair (X, τ) where τ is a subfamily of L^X which contains $0, 1$ and is closed for any suprema and finite infima.

Definition 2.1: [7] Let (X, τ) be an L-topological space, $A \in L^X$ Then A is called an γ -open set if $A \leq \text{Int}(A) \vee \text{Cl}(\text{Int}(A))$. The complement of an γ -open set is called an γ -closed set. Also, $\gamma O(L^X)$ and $\gamma C(L^X)$ will always denote the family of all γ -open sets and γ -closed sets respectively. Obviously, $A \in \gamma O(L^X)$ if, and only if $A' \in \gamma O(L^X)$.

Definition 2.2: [7] Let (L^X, τ) be an L-topological space, $A, B \in L^X$. Let $\gamma \text{Int}(A) = \vee \{ \beta \in L^X \mid \beta \leq A, B \in \gamma O(L^X) \}$, $\gamma \text{Cl}(A) = \wedge \{ \beta \in L^X \mid A \leq \beta, B \in \gamma C(L^X) \}$. Then $\gamma \text{Int}(A)$ and $\gamma \text{Cl}(A)$ are called the γ -interior and γ -closure of A respectively.

Definition 2.3: Two L-fuzzy sets A, B of an L-topological space (X, τ) are called γ -separated if $\gamma \text{Cl}(A) \wedge (B) = A \wedge \gamma \text{Cl}(B) = \underline{0}$.

Definition 2.4: In an L-topological space (X, τ) , an L-fuzzy set D is called γ - connected if D cannot be represented as a union of two γ - separated nonnull sets.

Definition 2.5: For two L-topological spaces (X, τ) and (Y, σ) , a mapping $f: X \rightarrow Y$ is called an γ -irresolute mapping if $f^{-1}(B)$ is γ -closed in (X, τ) for each γ -closed set B in (Y, σ) .

Lemma 2.6: [12] Let $A, B \in L^X$ and $A \leq B$. If $1 \in M(L)$, then $A' \vee B \neq \underline{1}$.

Lemma 2.7: [3] In a L-topological space (X, τ) , an L-fuzzy set D is called connected if there does not exist closed sets A, B such that $DA, DB, D' \leq A, D \leq B, D' \vee A \vee B = \underline{0}, D \wedge A \wedge B = \underline{0}$.

3. γ -Connectedness of L-Fuzzy Sets:

Definition 3.1: Let (X, τ) be an L-topological space, $D \in L^X$. D is called γ -connected if there does not exist γ -closed sets A, B such that $D' \leq A, D \leq B, D' \vee A \vee B = \underline{1}, D \wedge A \wedge B = \underline{0}$.

Example 3.2: Let $X_1 \cap X_2 = \emptyset, X = X_1 \cup X_2, L = [0, 1]$. Defined fuzzy set $(C_a, C_b) \in [0, 1]^X$ as follows:

$$(C_a, C_b)(x) = \begin{cases} a & \text{if } x \in X_1; \\ a & \text{if } x \in X_2; \end{cases}$$

Take $\beta = \{ (C_{0.4}, C_1), (C_1, C_{0.4}), (C_{0.5}, C_0), (C_{0.7}, C_0), (C_0, C_{0.7}) \}$

Let δ be a $[0, 1]$ -topology generated by β on X . Now we prove that $(C_{0.5}, C_0)$ is γ - connected. In fact, suppose that $(C_{0.5}, C_{0.5})$ is γ -connected. In fact, suppose that $(C_{0.5}, C_{0.5})$ is not γ - connected. Then there exist two γ - closed sets A, B such that $(C_{0.5}, C_{0.5}) \leq A, (C_{0.5}, C_{0.5}) \leq B, (C_{0.5}, C_{0.5})' \vee A \vee B = \underline{1}, (C_{0.5}, C_{0.5}) \wedge A \wedge B = \underline{0}$. This implies that

$(C_{0.5}, C_{0.5}) \leq A, (C_{0.5}, C_{0.5}) \leq B = \underline{1}, A \wedge B = \underline{0}$. Obviously A (or B) satisfying $A \wedge B = \underline{0}$, must be in $(C_\alpha, C_0), (C_0, C_\alpha) | \alpha \in [0.6, 0.7]$. But any two γ -closed sets in $\{(C_\alpha, C_0), (C_0, C_\alpha) | \alpha \in [0.6, 0.7]\}$ does not satisfy $A \vee B = \underline{1}$. Therefore $(C_{0.5}, C_{0.5})$ is γ -connected.

Theorem 3.3: Let (X, τ) be an L -topological space, $D \in L^X$. If $1 \in M(L)$ then the following conditions are equivalent.

- (1) D is γ -connected.
- (2) There does not exist γ -closed sets A, B such that $D \wedge A \neq \underline{0}, D \wedge B \neq \underline{0}, D' \vee A \vee B = \underline{1}, D \wedge A \wedge B = \underline{0}$.
- (3) There does not exist γ -open sets, U, V such that $D \leq U, D \leq V, D' \vee U \vee V = \underline{1}, D \wedge U \wedge V = \underline{0}$.
- (4) There does not exist γ -open sets, U, V such that $D \wedge U \neq \underline{0}, D \wedge V \neq \underline{0}, D' \vee U \vee V = \underline{1}, D \wedge U \wedge V = \underline{0}$.

Proof: (1) \Rightarrow (2). Suppose that there exist γ -closed sets A and B such that $D \wedge A \neq \underline{0}, D \wedge B \neq \underline{0}, D' \vee A \vee B = \underline{1}, D \wedge A \wedge B = \underline{0}$. Then obviously we have that $D' \vee A \vee B = \underline{1}, D \wedge A \wedge B = \underline{0}$. In this case, we can prove that $D \leq A, D \leq B$. In fact, if $D \leq A$, then $D \wedge A \wedge B = D \wedge B = \underline{0}$.

(2) \Rightarrow (3). Suppose that there exists γ -open sets U and V such that $D \leq U, D \leq V, D' \vee U \vee V = \underline{1}, D \wedge U \wedge V = \underline{0}$. Put $A = U', B = V'$. Obviously we have $D' \vee A \vee B = \underline{1}, D \wedge A \wedge B = \underline{0}$. In this case, we can prove that $D \wedge A \neq \underline{0}, D \wedge B \neq \underline{0}$. In fact, if $D \wedge A = \underline{0}$, then $D' \vee U = D' \vee A' = \underline{1}$, hence by Lemma 2.6 we obtain that $D \leq U$, which contradicts $D \leq U$.

(3) \Rightarrow (4) is analogous to (1) \Rightarrow (2)

(4) \Rightarrow (1) is analogous to (2) \Rightarrow (3).

Theorem 3.4: Let D be an γ -connected set in (X, τ) . If $D \leq E \leq \gamma Cl(D)$, then E is also an γ -connected set.

Proof: Suppose that E is not γ -connected. Then there exist two γ -closed sets A and B such that $E \leq A, E \leq B, E' \vee A \vee B = \underline{1}, E \wedge A \wedge B = \underline{0}$. Hence $D' \vee A \vee B = \underline{0}, D \wedge A \wedge B = \underline{0}$. In fact, we also have that $D \leq A, D \leq B$ (If $D \leq A$, then $E \leq \gamma Cl(D) \leq A$, which contradicts $E \leq A$). This shows that D is not γ -connected in (X, τ) , which contradicts that D is γ -connected. Therefore E is γ -connected.

Lemma 3.5: Let (X, τ) be an L -topological space and $D, E \in L^X$. Then D, E are γ -separated if, and only if there exists two γ -closed set A, V such that $D \leq A, E \leq B$ and $(D \vee E) \wedge A \wedge B = \underline{0}$.

Proof: If there exist two γ -closed sets A, B such that $D \leq A, E \leq B$ and $(D \vee E) \wedge A \wedge B = \underline{0}$, then we have that $(D \wedge \gamma Cl(E)) \vee (\gamma Cl(D) \wedge E) \leq (D \wedge B) \vee (E \wedge A) = \underline{0}$. This shows that D, E are γ -separated. Conversely, if D, E and γ -separated, then $(D \wedge \gamma Cl(E)) \vee (\gamma Cl(D) \wedge E) = \underline{0}$. Take $A = \gamma Cl(D)$ and $B = \gamma Cl(E)$. Then $(D \vee E) \wedge A \wedge B = (D \vee E) \wedge (\gamma Cl(D) \wedge \gamma Cl(E)) = D \wedge \gamma Cl(E) \vee \gamma Cl(D) \wedge E = \underline{0}$.

Theorem 3.6: Let D and E be two γ -connected L -fuzzy sets in an L -topological space (X, τ) . If D and E are γ -separated, then $D \vee E$ is γ -connected.

Proof: Suppose that $D \vee E$ is not γ -connected. Then there exist two γ -closed sets A and B such that $D \vee E \leq A, D \vee E \leq B, (D \vee E)' \vee A \vee B = \underline{1}, (D \vee E) \wedge A \wedge B = \underline{0}$. Hence we have that $D' \vee A \vee B = \underline{1}, D \wedge A \wedge B = \underline{0}, E' \vee A \vee B = \underline{1}, E \wedge A \wedge B = \underline{0}$. By $D \vee E \leq A$. We have that $D \leq A$ or $E \leq A$. Suppose that $D \leq A$. Then we must have that $D \leq B$. Since D is γ -connected. Further by $D \vee E \leq B$ we obtain that $E \leq B$. In this case it follows that $D \vee E \leq A$. Therefore by $(D \vee E) \wedge A \wedge B = \underline{0}$ and Lemma 3.5 we know that D, E are γ -separated, which contradicts that D, E are not γ -separated. The proof is completed.

Theorem 3.7: Let $\{D_t | t \in \Omega\}$ be a family of γ -connected L -fuzzy sets. If $\bigwedge_{t \in \Omega} D_t \neq \underline{0}$, then $\bigvee_{t \in \Omega} D_t$ is γ -connected.

Theorem 3.9: Let $f: (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ be an γ -irresolute mapping. If D is γ -connected in (X, τ) , then so is $f(D)$ in (Y, σ) .

Proof: Suppose that $f(D)$ is not γ -connected in (Y, σ) . Then there exist two γ -closed sets A, B in (Y, σ) such that $f(D) \leq A, f(D) \leq B, f(D)' \vee A \vee B = \underline{1}, f(D) \wedge A \wedge B = \underline{0}$. Thus by $D \leq f^{-1}(f(D))$ or $D' \leq f^{-1}(f(D)')$ we have that $D \leq f^{-1}(A), D \leq f^{-1}(B), D' \vee f^{-1}(A) \vee f^{-1}(B) = \underline{1}, D \wedge f^{-1}(A) \wedge f^{-1}(B) = \underline{0}$. Since f is γ -irresolute mapping, $f^{-1}(A)$ and $f^{-1}(B)$ are γ -closed set in (X, τ) . This shows that D is not γ -connected in (X, τ) which contradicts that D is γ -connected. Therefore $f(D)$ is γ -connected in (Y, σ) .

Theorem 3.10: Let (X, τ) be an L -topological space and $D \in L^X$. Then D is γ -connected if, and only if for any two co-prime elements $a, b \leq D$, there exists a γ -connected set E such that $a, b \leq E \leq D$.

Proof: The necessity is obvious. Now we prove the sufficiency, suppose that D is not γ -connected in (X, τ) . Then there exist two γ -closed sets A, B in (X, τ) such that $D \leq A, D \leq B, D' \vee A \vee B = \underline{1}, D \wedge A \wedge B = \underline{0}$. Take two coprime elements $a, b \leq D$ such that $a \leq A$ and $b \leq B$. Let E be an γ -connected set satisfying $a, b \leq E \leq D$. We have that $E \leq A, E \leq B, E' \vee A \vee B = \underline{1}, E \wedge A \wedge B = \underline{0}$. This shows that E is not γ -connected in (X, τ) a contradiction.

Definition 3.11: Let (X, τ) be an L -topological space, $D \in L^X$ and F denote the set of all γ -closed sets in (X, τ) . A mapping $P: M^*(D) \rightarrow F$ is called an γ -remote neighborhood mapping on D , if for each $e \in M^*(D)$, it holds that $e \leq P(e)$.

Example 3.12: Let $X_1 \cap X_2 = \emptyset, X = X_1 \cup X_2, L = [0, 1]$. Defined fuzzy set $(C_a, C_b) \in [0, 1]^X$ as follows.

$$(C_a, C_b)(x) = \begin{cases} a & \text{if } x \in X_1 \\ b & \text{if } x \in X_2 \end{cases}$$

Let $\delta = \{\emptyset, \underline{1}, (C_{0.5}, C_{0.5})\}$. Then δ is a $[0, 1]$ – topology on X . $\forall e \in M(L^X)$, define

$$P(e) = \begin{cases} (C_{0.5}, C_{0.5}) & \text{if } e \not\leq (C_{0.5}, C_{0.5}); \\ 0 & \text{if } e \leq (C_{0.5}, C_{0.5}); \end{cases}$$

Then P is a γ remote neighborhood mapping.

Theorem 3.13: Let (X, T) be an L – topological space, $D \in L^X$. Then D is γ connected if, and only if for any two coprime elements $a, b \in M^*(D)$ and any γ – remote neighborhood mapping $P: M^*(D) \rightarrow F$, there exist finite many coprime elements $e_1 = a, e_2, \dots, e_n = b$ in D such that $D' \vee P(e_i) \vee P(e_{i+1}) \neq \underline{1}, i = 1, 2, \dots, n - 1$.

Proof: Suppose that D is not γ connected. Then there exist two γ - closed sets A, B such that $D \not\leq A, D \not\leq B, D' \vee A \vee B = \underline{1}, D \wedge A \wedge B = \underline{0}$. Define a pre-remote neighborhood mapping $P: M^*(D) \rightarrow F$, such that $\forall e \in M^*(D)$,

$$P(e) = \begin{cases} A & \text{if } e \not\leq B; \\ B & \text{if } e \leq B. \end{cases}$$

Take $a, b \in M^*(D)$ such that $a \not\leq A$ and $b \not\leq B$. Then for arbitrary finite many coprime elements $e_1 = a, e_2, \dots, e_n = b$ in D , there exists an i such that $D' \vee P(e_i) \vee D' \vee P(e_{i+1}) = \underline{1}$, this contradicts the condition of Theorem. Thus the sufficiency is proved. Conversely, suppose that there exist two coprime elements $a, b \in M^*(D)$ and an γ -remote neighborhood mapping $P: M^*(D) \rightarrow F$ such that for arbitrary finite many coprime elements $e_1 = a, e_2, \dots, e_n = b$ in D , the following fact is not true: $D' \vee P(e_i) \vee D' \vee P(e_{i+1}) \neq \underline{1}, i = 1, 2, \dots, n - 1$. In this case, we say that a and b cannot be linked. Let $A = \{e \in M^*(D) : a \text{ and } e \text{ can be linked}\}, B = \{e \in M^*(D) : a \text{ and } e \text{ cannot be linked}\}$. Then $\forall c \in A$ and $\forall d \in B$, we have that $D' \vee P(c) \vee D' \vee P(d) = 1$. Put $A = \bigwedge \{P(c) : c \in A\} \wedge \bigwedge \{P(d) : d \in B\}$. Obviously we have that $D \wedge A, D \wedge B, D' \vee A \vee B = \underline{1}, D' \vee A \vee B = \underline{0}$. This shows that D is not γ -connected.

References:

1. D. M. Ali .Some other types of fuzzy connectedness. Fuzzy sets and systems, 16(1992).55-61.
2. D. M. Ali and A.K.Srivastava, On fuzzy connectedness, fuzzy sets and systems, 28 (1988), 203 – 208.
3. S. Z. Bai, Strong Connectedness in L -topological spaces. JFuzzy Math, 3(1995), 751 – 759
4. G. Baasubramanian and P. Sundaram, On some generalizations of fuzzy continuous functions. Fuzzy sets and systems 86(1997) 93 – 100.
5. G.Gierz, et al. A compendium of continuous lattices, Springer – Verlag. Berlin, 1980
6. P. P. Pu and Y. M. Liu. Fuzzy topology I, Neighborhood structure of a fuzzy point and Moore-Smith convergence, J. Math. Anal. Appl, 76(1980) 571-599.
7. P. Senthil Kumar and S. Sangeetha, On Fuzzy γ open sets in L – fuzzy topological spaces (submitted)
8. F.G. Shi and C.Y. Zheng. Connectivity in fuzzy Topological molecular lattices, Fuzzy sets and systems, 29 (1989), 363 – 370
9. N. Turanli and D. Coker. On some types of fuzzy connectedness in fuzzy topological spaces. Fuzzy sets and systems, 60 (1993), 97 – 102.
10. G. J. Wang. Theorey of topological molecular lattices, Fuzzy sets and systems 47 (1992). 351 – 376.
11. G. J. Wang, Theory of L – fuzzy topological spaces, Shaanxi Normal University Press. Xi'an 1988.
12. G. M. Wang and F.G. Shi, Local connectedness of L -fuzzy topological spaces. Fuzzy systems and Mathematics, 10(4) (1996), 51 – 55
13. D. S. Zhao and G.J. Wang, A new kind of fuzzy connectivity, Fuzzy Mathematics 15-22.
14. C. Y. Zheng. Connectedness of Fuzzy topological spaces, fuzzy mathematics 2(1982). 56 – 66